

Development and Evaluation of an AI Chatbot for Educational Support Utilizing Lecture Materials

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Abstract: In modern university education, managing diverse student inquiries poses a significant burden on instructors, highlighting the increasing importance of personalized support. To address this challenge, we developed an AI chatbot that provides responses tailored to specific course content, using lecture materials and video transcripts. The system is built on the OpenAI API (GPT-5) and integrates Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) technology. The developed chatbot is deployed in two courses, "Requirements Engineering" and "Career Design for IT Engineers," and evaluated with 80 university students. Evaluation results indicate that approximately 80% of the students positively rated the chatbot's responses as "helpful", confirming its high utility in aspects such as organizing and re-presenting lecture content, suggesting future actions, and offering diverse perspectives. Furthermore, the use of past student comments and instructor responses as learning data proved highly valuable as a supplementary resource for enhancing student understanding. This research shows AI chatbots are practical tools for personalized support and reducing instructor workload. Future work aims to build a more personalized and effective learning support environment by incorporating features such as tracking individual student learning progress and enabling instructors to analyze conversation logs.

Keywords: AI chatbot; educational support; Large Language Model; Retrieval-Augmented Generation Introduction

I. Introduction

In recent years, the importance of personalized support in university education has increased to deepen each student's understanding. Among these, responding to diverse comments and questions submitted during or after classes has become a significant burden for instructors.

To address this issue, developing an AI chatbot that responds automatically 24 hours a day, 365 days a year, is expected to reduce instructors' workload and improve students' comprehension. In this paper, we developed an AI chatbot that provides responses tailored to specific course content, using lecture materials and lecture video transcripts. OpenAI API (GPT-5) was adopted as the language model [1].

Previously, various learning support systems using generative AI have been reported, including those that focus on reflection in mathematics learning and on programming instruction. This research distinguishes itself from prior work by providing flexible responses to student comments on lectures and by using learning logs for educational analysis.

Recent advancements in technologies such as LangChain [5], Streamlit [6], and GPTs [10][11] have expanded the possibilities for more dynamic and responsive chatbots. This research distinguishes itself by integrating Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) [8]. Furthermore, an evaluation involving 80 university students was conducted, providing practical insights into the chatbot's effectiveness.

This paper is organized as follows. We shall review related work on AI chatbots for educational support and highlight the uniqueness of this research in Section II. Section III describes the AI chatbot's system architecture, implementation, response-processing flow, prompt design, and response examples. Section IV presents the evaluation results based on student feedback in two courses. Section V discusses the system's effectiveness and possible improvements. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper and outlines directions for future work.

II. Related Work

Existing research has demonstrated the effectiveness of AI chatbots in various educational support contexts.

However, many of these systems have relied on static FAQ datasets or have lacked adaptability to specific course content. This chapter reviews key related studies, highlighting their methodologies, findings, and how our work differentiates itself.

A. Studies on Language Learning Support Systems

Yang et al. [2] proposed a dialogue system to support vocabulary acquisition, with a focus on “Katakana words,” which are particularly difficult for Japanese language learners, particularly foreigners, to master. This system used a fine-tuned GPT-2 with keyword extraction to support vocabulary retention and conversational skills. While their research targeted a specific language learning domain (Katakana words) with the primary goal of enhancing vocabulary retention and conversational skills, it demonstrated the effectiveness of domain-specific chatbot systems in supporting learners’ understanding.

B. Studies on Chatbots in University Settings and Programming Education

Belhaj et al. [4] aimed to assess the feasibility of a chatbot-driven survey approach at a Moroccan university as a new method to address common issues with response quality in traditional web surveys. Their system used NLP, ML, Facebook Messenger, and Chatfuel, incorporating daily questions and university information to maintain dialogue.

Rajala, J. et al. [3] investigated how students perceive and utilize ChatGPT as a tutoring chatbot in a computer science course. They integrated ChatGPT into private Microsoft Teams discussion groups, enabling students to use ChatGPT and related technologies for assignments. Students used it for purposes such as debugging code, tutoring, and promoting understanding. Positive impacts on understanding, learning, and creativity outweighed negative impacts, though many students found output reliability challenging. Both studies highlight the diverse applications of chatbots in university contexts.

C. Comparative Experiment on AI Tutor Effectiveness

A study conducted at Harvard University compared the AI tutor “PS2 Pal” with in-class active learning sessions in an undergraduate physics course through a large-scale comparative experiment [13]. The AI tutor provided step-by-step guidance aligned with the course materials and incorporated design principles, including reducing cognitive load, scaffolding informed by learning science, and delivering timely feedback. The

analysis revealed that students who received lectures from the AI tutor achieved higher learning outcomes compared to those who attended human-led lectures. Additionally, students using the AI tutor completed the learning tasks more quickly than those attending in-class sessions.

Furthermore, the AI tutor group reported significantly higher levels of engagement and motivation. This study demonstrates the potential of AI tutors to enhance both learning outcomes and motivation. It suggests their practical use in flipped classroom models, particularly for pre-class preparation and individualized learning support.

D. Novelty and Contribution of This Work

This research develops an AI chatbot tailored to university lecture content, using Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) with actual lecture materials and transcripts to ensure high contextual accuracy. Unlike systems relying on static FAQs or broad general knowledge, it dynamically retrieves course-specific content to provide precise, context-aware responses aligned with the lecture scope.

Compared with prior work, our chatbot handles a wider range of topics than Yang et al.’s domain-specific vocabulary support system. It focuses on educational dialogue rather than survey collection as in Belhaj et al.’s approach. Unlike Rajala et al.’s open-ended tutoring chatbot, it uses structured retrieval to maintain fidelity to verified lecture content. While the Harvard AI tutor study highlights improved learning outcomes and reduced study time through guided instruction, our system offers flexible, on-demand responses that support both immediate clarification and self-directed review.

III. System Overview and Implementation

A. System Overview

The developed chatbot system automatically generates context-aware responses to student comments using lecture materials. It is built on OpenAI’s GPT-5 and employs Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) [8] for dynamic response generation.

Figure 1 illustrates the overall architecture of the system, which consists of the four main stages:

- (1) The user enters a question or comment through the Streamlit-based user interface.
- (2) The system searches Lecture Materials and Transcripts using the RAG component.

(3) The retrieved content is combined with a predefined prompt template. This process determines the structure, tone, and level of detail for the chatbot's reply.

(4) GPT-5 generates the final answer based on the constructed prompt. The response is then displayed in the Streamlit UI, completing the interaction loop between the user and the system.

Although these stages are visually represented in the figure without explicit numbering, each component corresponds to a core step in the chatbot's processing flow.

The system uses LangChain [5] for context retrieval and prompt management and is implemented as a web application built with Streamlit [6]. Lecture materials, such as PDF slides and video transcripts, are vectorized and searched for relevant content in response to student inputs.

Figure 1: Overall Architecture of the Chatbot System

B. Implementation Environment and Configuration

The system is developed in Python 3.10, using the OpenAI API, FAISS [7], and LangChain for embedding, retrieval, and prompt composition. Streamlit is used to build the user interface. Development and deployment were carried out on AWS Cloud9 [9] and Streamlit Community Cloud. To ensure open access for students, the chatbot URL was shared via the Moodle course page, allowing browser-based use without login.

While GPT Builder [10,11] enables rapid chatbot creation, it imposes limitations on free users. Therefore, we opted to build the system using the API to ensure open access for educational use.

The following is a list of parameters and their values.

Chunking: chunk_size=800, chunk_overlap=100, separators ["\n\n", "\n", ". "].

Retrieval: Top-k=1 (test phase: we retrieve only the single most similar chunk to simplify evaluation, stabilize latency, and yield a deterministic answer).

Embedding: text-embedding-3-large (3072-dim), selected for higher retrieval accuracy on materials with extensive domain-specific terminology.

LLM decoding: temperature = 0.2, top_p = 1.0, max_tokens = 800.

C. Response Processing Flow

The chatbot's processing flow includes the following six steps:

- (1) Comment input via Streamlit UI.
- (2) Conversion to vector form using OpenAI embeddings.
- (3) Retrieval of top-n similar lecture segments using FAISS.
- (4) Prompt generation via LangChain using the retrieved content.
- (5) Response generation with GPT-5.
- (6) Response display and logging to Google Sheets.

D. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) in Our System

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) has a two-stage architecture that (i) retrieves task-relevant documents from an external knowledge store and (ii) conditions the language model on those retrieved passages to generate grounded responses. In our system, RAG ensures that answers remain faithful to the course content and reduces unsupported ("hallucinated") statements—an essential requirement in educational settings.

Knowledge sources and indexing.

Our knowledge base comprises:

1. All slide decks for 15-week classes (PDF)
2. Transcripts of all 15-week lecture videos (plain text)
3. Past student comments paired with instructor responses (plain text)

These materials are segmented into slides or paragraphs, embedded with OpenAI embeddings, and indexed with FAISS for similarity search. At inference time, the student's input is embedded, the vector index is queried, and the top four most relevant chunks are retrieved. Currently, the single most relevant chunk (top-1) is incorporated into the structured prompt, together with the system instruction and the user's question, and passed to GPT-5 to generate the final response. This design maximizes precision by grounding the answer in the most contextually similar passage, thereby minimizing irrelevant content in the prompt.

Handling low-relevance cases.

When the retrieved chunk contains insufficient or loosely related information, the system relies on prompt instructions to determine the response strategy. Specifically, the language model is instructed to either (a) indicate that the question falls outside the lecture scope while optionally providing relevant general knowledge related to the lecture, or (b) add relevant general knowledge from the lecture's subject area to complete the answer when necessary. This decision is made by the language model based on the retrieved content, as no explicit similarity-threshold mechanism is currently implemented.

Design choices.

We prioritize high-precision retrieval over recall by focusing on the top-1 result for generation. Chunks are kept short and semantically coherent to avoid diluting the prompt with unrelated information. The system handles both Japanese and English transparently, generating responses in the same language as the user's question. All interactions are logged in Google Sheets for subsequent analysis of response quality and student needs. This behavior aligns with the lecture content and provides reliable study guidance.

E. Prompt Design

Prompt design is essential for enabling the AI chatbot to generate accurate and context-aware responses based on lecture materials. In this system, prompts are dynamically constructed using LangChain, which integrates retrieved content with a predefined structure tailored for educational use.

Each prompt consists of three elements: (1) system instructions defining the assistant's role, (2) retrieved lecture content, and (3) the student's question or comment. The prompt is then passed to GPT-5 for response generation.

To optimize the prompt format, we adopted an iterative refinement process:

1. An initial template was generated using ChatGPT, based on the intended use case and tone.
2. The prompt was tested with actual lecture data and student inputs.
3. If the output was unsatisfactory, the template was revised and tested again.
4. This cycle was repeated to improve clarity, consistency, and educational effectiveness.

This approach enabled flexible and structured responses aligned with lecture content. The prompt

format can be readily adapted to future updates to course materials or instructional goals.

F. Response Examples

Figure 2 presents the dialogue interface of the developed chatbot and a representative student question with its corresponding chatbot response. The chatbot can also show a Japanese-language response when the student's input is in Japanese, demonstrating that the system can provide language-sensitive explanations. The chatbot interface maintains a consistent style and tone while delivering detailed, user-friendly explanations tailored to the course content, regardless of the language used.

Figure 2: Example chatbot response

IV. Evaluation

This chapter details the evaluation conducted to verify the effectiveness of the developed AI chatbot. The system was deployed for actual use by students in two courses, "Requirements Engineering" and "Career Design for IT Engineers", and their dialogue logs and evaluation data on the chatbot's responses were collected via Google Sheets. Specifically, the degree to which the chatbot's responses were helpful to students was set as the primary evaluation metric, and quantitative data through surveys and qualitative feedback through free-text responses were collected. These collected data were analyzed using ChatGPT. The purpose of this chapter is to clarify the chatbot's utility and areas for improvement through this analysis, and to discuss the practical potential of AI chatbots in educational settings and the challenges associated with designing more effective responses.

A. Student Evaluation in Requirements Engineering

This section presents the evaluation results of the chatbot in the "Requirements Engineering" course

provided for graduate students majoring in information technology. 70% of enrolled students are Japanese, and the remaining are international students; thus, we set up the AI chatbot to respond in each student's preferred language.

The student evaluation indicated that, of 13 students, 11 (approximately 85%) rated the chatbot's responses as "helpful" ("Very helpful": 2; "Quite helpful": 9), indicating a strong positive reception.

The main reasons for this positive evaluation were the chatbot's ability to "organize and re-present lecture content," allowing students to reconfirm key points rather than merely responding to their impressions. The "suggestion of future actions" was also praised, as the chatbot indicated what to do and how to approach the next steps. Furthermore, the "provision of diverse perspectives" was noted, where exposure to different ideas and viewpoints from other students contributed to their learning.

B. Student Evaluation in Career Design for IT Engineers

This section presents the evaluation results for the chatbot in the "Career Design for IT Engineers" course, offered to undergraduate students in their second academic year. All enrolled students in this class are Japanese.

In this course, among 67 students, 52 (approximately 80%) rated the chatbot's responses as "helpful" ("Very helpful": 10; "Quite helpful": 42), indicating a largely positive perception.

Key reasons for this positive evaluation included "concrete and clear explanations," in which the chatbot provided specific examples and concrete interpretations rather than abstract ones. The "suggestion of action guidelines" was also frequently mentioned, as the chatbot proposed concrete improvement plans and the next steps. Additionally, the "organization of key points and precautions" contributed to improved understanding by summarizing important points and cautions based on student comments.

C. Cross-Course Evaluation Distribution

The student evaluation of the chatbot deployed in this study yielded positive results in both courses. Figure 3 compares the distribution of student evaluations of the chatbot's usefulness across the "Requirements Engineering" and "Career Design for IT Engineers" courses. Approximately 85% of students in Requirements Engineering and 80% in Career Design for IT Engineers rated the chatbot as "helpful", suggesting that this system has the potential to widely

contribute to student learning support even in different course characteristics.

Figure 3: Student Evaluation of Chatbot Usefulness Across Courses

D. Analysis and Overall Discussion of Past Learning Resource Utilization

This research utilized previously collected "student comments and instructor responses" as training data to enhance the chatbot's response quality. This material was structured with the expectation that it would serve as a foundation for improving the quality and suitability of responses when students use the chatbot for their inquiries. This section examines the extent to which these prior materials were helpful to students and how they were used, based on an analysis of survey results and free-text descriptions from both courses.

A survey was administered to students to assess the usefulness of the "past student comments and instructor response materials" referenced by the chatbot.

- **Requirements Engineering:** Approximately 60% of students who viewed the past materials rated them positively ("Very helpful": 1 student, "Quite helpful": 7 students).

- **Career Design for IT Engineers:** Approximately half of the students who viewed the past materials rated them positively ("Very helpful": 4 students, "Quite helpful": 28 students).

Common reasons cited across both courses for the helpfulness of past materials include:

- **Ability to understand others' perspectives:** Students commented that seeing other students' questions and impressions helped them deepen their understanding.

- **Representing their questions:** Students found responses to other students' questions helpful because they addressed the duplicate content they were unsure about.

- **Concrete and clear explanations:** The materials were praised for providing specific and easy-to-understand explanations in response to questions, rather than abstract ones.

- **Suggestion of action guidelines:** Beyond simple explanations, the materials were noted for suggesting improvement plans and the next steps in response to their comments.
- **Organization of key points and precautions:** Students found that the materials summarized important points and precautions from their writings, which deepened their understanding.

These results confirm that past materials are not merely sources of information but are also used as supplementary learning tools to deepen student understanding and as learning data for the chatbot. This suggests that not only real-time responses provided by the chatbot, but also the accumulation of past Q&A, are effective in meeting diverse student learning needs.

V. Discussion

We shall discuss the effectiveness, insights gained, and areas for future improvement based on the AI chatbot's operational results and student evaluations presented in Section IV. Specifically, the evaluation results from the "Requirements Engineering" and "Career Design for IT Engineers" courses will be examined in depth, clarifying the chatbot's role and the challenges tailored to each course's characteristics.

A. Discussion on Requirements Engineering

The student evaluation for "Requirements Engineering" indicates that the chatbot was well received in the course. The fact that approximately 85% of students rated it as "helpful" strongly supports the system's utility for student learning support.

The "organization and re-presentation of lecture content," cited as a primary reason for positive evaluation, suggests that the chatbot functioned not merely as a Q&A tool but as a means for students to review course material and reconfirm key points. This is a result of the ability to provide accurate information specific to the lecture materials through the RAG configuration. Furthermore, the chatbot's "suggestion of future actions" and "provision of diverse perspectives" suggest that it is designed to encourage students to think critically and deepen their learning by considering multiple viewpoints. This indicates that the prompt design, which encouraged empathetic and supplementary explanations beyond just answering questions, was successful.

Characteristics of this course include the need for a deeper understanding of specialized terminology and methods, and the necessity to accommodate linguistic diversity due to the enrollment of international students. The chatbot's prompt design, which supports automatic

Japanese/English switching and adds procedures and background explanations in addition to definitions, is thought to have met these needs and contributed to students' understanding.

B. Discussion on Career Design for IT Engineers

In the "Career Design for IT Engineer" course, approximately 80% of students also rated the chatbot's responses positively, demonstrating its effectiveness as a learning support tool.

Points particularly praised in this course were "concrete and clear explanations," "suggestion of action guidelines," and "organization of key points and precautions". This suggests that the chatbot effectively met the needs of students who harbored career-related anxieties and sought concrete action guidelines. The prompt design, which maintained a polite and empathetic tone while proposing improvement plans and next steps in response to comments, is considered to have provided support that led to students' concrete learning and actions.

Compared to "Requirements Engineering," this course showed a tendency for students to seek more practical advice and personalized suggestions tailored to their circumstances. The chatbot's ability to meet these needs to some extent suggests the potential for personalized support for learners with specific goals, rather than merely providing generic information.

C. Discussion on the Utilization of Past Learning Resources

The analysis of the use of "past student comments and instructor responses" in both courses confirmed that these materials are supplementary and valuable for student learning. The fact that approximately 50-60% of students rated this material positively indicates not only its value as learning data for the chatbot but also that exposure to others' questions and instructors' responses contributes to a deeper understanding.

Specifically, evaluation criteria such as "ability to understand others' perspectives" and "representing their questions" underscore the importance of providing learners with opportunities to encounter similar questions and diverse perspectives before formulating their own questions. This implies that, beyond providing real-time responses, structuring and making past knowledge assets searchable through the chatbot can enrich the entire learning process. Therefore, using high-quality historical dialogue data as the chatbot's knowledge base is highly effective not only for improving response accuracy but also for promoting autonomous student learning.

D. Overall Discussion and Challenges

The AI chatbot developed in this paper was confirmed to be a practical tool for both student learning support and reducing instructor workload through lecture material-based responses. RAG technology and meticulous prompt design demonstrated the potential to address diverse needs, given the characteristics of each course. In particular, the high student evaluations of the organization of lecture content, the proposed action guidelines, and the provision of diverse perspectives indicate that it has overcome the limitations of the inherent flexibility of conventional FAQ-based chatbots.

However, future issues still remain. There is a need to strengthen control mechanisms to prevent irrelevant or speculative responses when student questions fall outside the scope of the lecture materials. Furthermore, there is room for improvement in the naturalness of conversation and the clarity of explanations for specialized terms. These challenges are expected to be addressed through improvements in LLM hallucination issues, RAG search accuracy, and further refinement of prompt engineering.

Overall, this research demonstrated that AI chatbots in university education can serve as partners that deepen student learning and qualitatively enhance instructors' educational activities, rather than merely as providers of information. Customization according to the needs of individual courses and continuous improvement will be key to maximizing its potential.

VI. Conclusion and Future Work

This research demonstrated the potential of an AI chatbot, leveraging lecture materials and video transcripts, to support student learning and reduce instructor workload. By building a system based on OpenAI's GPT-5 model and integrating RAG technology, it was shown that accurate and flexible responses tailored to specific course content are possible.

Based on results from the practical deployment and student evaluations in the two courses, we confirmed the chatbot's utility, with approximately 80%-85% of students rating its responses as "helpful". Specifically, high utility was observed in organizing and representing lecture content, suggesting future action guidelines, and providing diverse perspectives. Furthermore, using past student comments and instructor responses as learning data proved highly useful as a supplementary learning tool, enhancing student understanding and improving response quality.

These results show that AI chatbots can overcome the limitations of FAQs and serve as personalized support tools. Future efforts will focus on limiting responses strictly to lecture content to avoid irrelevant or speculative answers. Improvements in RAG accuracy and prompt design will help detect and appropriately reject out-of-scope questions.

We also plan to introduce basic personalization features by utilizing Moodle data (e.g., student ID, history) to provide more adaptive responses. Moreover, analyzing chatbot logs may provide valuable feedback to instructors to support the continuous improvement of teaching materials and chatbot performance.

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